

SOME SMARANDACHE-TYPE MULTIPLICATIVE FUNCTIONS

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This note considers eleven particular families of interrelated multiplicative functions, many of which are listed in Smarandache's problems.

These are multiplicative in the sense that a function $f(n)$ has the property that for any two coprime positive integers a and b , i.e. with a highest common factor (also known as greatest common divisor) of 1, then $f(a*b)=f(a)*f(b)$. It immediately follows that $f(1)=1$ unless all other values of $f(n)$ are 0. An example is $d(n)$, the number of divisors of n . This multiplicative property allows such functions to be uniquely defined on the positive integers by describing the values for positive integer powers of primes. $d(p^i)=i+1$ if $i>0$; so $d(60) = d(2^2*3^1*5^1) = (2+1)*(1+1)*(1+1) = 12$.

Unlike $d(n)$, the sequences described below are a restricted subset of all multiplicative functions. In all of the cases considered here, $f(p^i)=p^{g(i)}$ for some function g which does not depend on p .

	Definition	Multiplicative with $p^i > p^{\dots}$
$A_m(n)$	Number of solutions to $x^m \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$	$i\text{-ceiling}[i/m]$
$B_m(n)$	Largest m^{th} power dividing n	$m*\text{floor}[i/m]$
$C_m(n)$	m^{th} root of largest m^{th} power dividing n	$\text{floor}[i/m]$
$D_m(n)$	m^{th} power-free part of n	$i-m*\text{floor}[i/m]$
$E_m(n)$	Smallest number x ($x>0$) such that $n*x$ is a perfect m^{th} power (Smarandache m^{th} power complements)	$m*\text{ceiling}[i/m]-i$
$F_m(n)$	Smallest m^{th} power divisible by n divided by largest m^{th} power which divides n	$m*(\text{ceiling}[i/m]-\text{floor}[i/m])$
$G_m(n)$	m^{th} root of smallest m^{th} power divisible by n divided by largest m^{th} power which divides n	$\text{ceiling}[i/m]-\text{floor}[i/m]$
$H_m(n)$	Smallest m^{th} power divisible by n (Smarandache $\wedge_m$ function (numbers))	$m*\text{ceiling}[i/m]$
$J_m(n)$	m^{th} root of smallest m^{th} power divisible by n (Smarandache Ceil Function of m^{th} Order)	$\text{ceiling}[i/m]$
$K_m(n)$	Largest m^{th} power-free number dividing n	$\min(i,m-1)$

	(Smarandache m^{th} power residues)	
$L_m(n)$	n divided by largest m^{th} power-free number dividing n	$\max(0, i-m+1)$

Relationships between the functions

Some of these definitions may appear to be similar; for example $D_m(n)$ and $K_m(n)$, but for $m > 2$ all of the functions are distinct (for some values of n given m). The following relationships follow immediately from the definitions:

$$B_m(n) = C_m(n)^m \quad (1)$$

$$n = B_m(n) * D_m(n) \quad (2)$$

$$F_m(n) = D_m(n) * E_m(n) \quad (3)$$

$$F_m(n) = G_m(n)^m \quad (4)$$

$$H_m(n) = n * E_m(n) \quad (5)$$

$$H_m(n) = B_m(n) * F_m(n) \quad (6)$$

$$H_m(n) = J_m(n)^m \quad (7)$$

$$n = K_m(n) * L_m(n) \quad (8)$$

These can also be combined to form new relationships; for example from (1), (4) and (7) we have

$$J_m(n) = C_m(n) * G_m(n) \quad (9)$$

Further relationships can also be derived easily. For example, looking at $A_m(n)$, a number x has the property $x^m \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$ if and only if x^m is divisible by n or in other words a multiple of $H_m(n)$, i.e. x is a multiple of $J_m(n)$. But $J_m(n)$ divides into n , so we have the pretty result that:

$$n = J_m(n) * A_m(n) \quad (10)$$

We could go on to construct a wide variety of further relationships, such as using (5), (7) and (10) to produce:

$$n^{m-1} = E_m(n) * A_m(n)^m \quad (11)$$

but instead we will note that $C_m(n)$ and $J_m(n)$ are sufficient to produce all of the functions from $A_m(n)$ through to $J_m(n)$:

$$A_m(n) = n / J_m(n) \quad (12)$$

$$B_m(n) = C_m(n)^m$$

$$C_m(n) = C_m(n)$$

$$D_m(n) = n / C_m(n)^m \quad (13)$$

$$E_m(n) = J_m(n)^m / n \quad (14)$$

$$F_m(n) = (J_m(n) / C_m(n))^m \quad (15)$$

$$G_m(n) = J_m(n) / C_m(n) \quad (16)$$

$$H_m(n) = J_m(n)^m$$

$$J_m(n) = J_m(n)$$

Clearly we could have done something similar by choosing one element each from two of the sets {A,E,H,J}, {B,C,D}, and {F,G}. The choice of C and J is partly based on the following attractive property which further deepens the multiplicative nature of these functions.

If $m = a * b$ then:

$$C_m(n) = C_a(C_b(n)) \quad (17)$$

$$J_m(n) = J_a(J_b(n)) \quad (18)$$

Duplicate functions when $m=2$...

When $m=2$, $D_2(n)$ is square-free and $F_2(n)$ is the smallest square which is a multiple of $D_2(n)$, so

$$F_2(n) = D_2(n)^2 \quad (19)$$

Using (3) and (4) we then have:

$$D_2(n) = E_2(n) = G_2(n) \quad (20)$$

and from (13) and (14) we have

$$n = C_2(n) * J_2(n) \quad (21)$$

so from (10) we get

$$A_2(n) = C_2(n) \quad (22)$$

... and when $m=1$

If $m=1$, all the functions described either produce 1 or n . The analogue of (20) is still true with

$$D_1(n)=E_1(n)=G_1(n)=1 \quad (23)$$

but curiously the analogue of (22) is not, since:

$$A_1(n)=1 \quad (24)$$

$$C_1(n)=n \quad (25)$$

The two remaining functions

All this leaves two slightly different functions to be considered: $K_m(n)$ and $L_m(n)$. They have little connection with the other sequences except for the fact that since $G_m(n)$ is square-free, and divides $D_m(n)$, $E_m(n)$, $F_m(n)$, and $G_m(n)$, none of which have any factor which is a higher power than m , we get:

$$G_m(n)=J_m(D_m(n))=J_m(E_m(n))=J_m(F_m(n))=J_m(G_m(n))=K_2(D_m(n))=K_2(E_m(n))=K_2(F_m(n))=K_2(G_m(n)) \quad (26)$$

and so with (8) and (10)

$$n/G_m(n)=A_m(D_m(n))=A_m(E_m(n))=A_m(F_m(n))=A_m(G_m(n))=L_2(D_m(n))=L_2(E_m(n))=L_2(F_m(n))=L_2(G_m(n)) \quad (27)$$

We also have the related convergence property that for any y , there is a z (e.g. $\text{floor}[\log_2(n)]$) for which

$$G_m(n)=J_m(n)=K_2(n) \text{ for any } n \leq y \text{ and any } m > z \quad (28)$$

$$A_m(n)=L_2(n) \text{ for any } n \leq y \text{ and any } m > z \quad (29)$$

There is a simple relation where

$$L_m(n)=L_a(L_b(n)) \text{ if } m+1=a+b \text{ and } a,b>0 \quad (29)$$

and in particular

$$L_m(n)=L_{m-1}(L_2(n)) \text{ if } m>1 \quad (30)$$

$$L_3(n)=L_2(L_2(n)) \quad (31)$$

$$L_4(n)=L_2(L_2(L_2(n))) \quad (32)$$

so with (8) we also have

$$K_m(n)=K_b(n)*K_a(n/K_b(n)) \text{ if } m+1=a+b \text{ and } a,b>0 \quad (33)$$

$$K_m(n)=K_{m-1}(n)*K_2(n/K_{m-1}(n)) \text{ if } m>1 \quad (34)$$

$$K_3(n)=K_2(n)*K_2(n/K_2(n)) \quad (35)$$

$$K_4(n) = K_2(n) * K_2(n/K_2(n)) * K_2(n/(K_2(n) * K_2(n/K_2(n)))) \quad (36)$$

Recording the functions

The values of all these functions for n up from $n=1$ to about 70 or more are listed in [Neil Sloane's Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences](#) for $m=2, 3$ and 4:

	$m=1$	$m=2$	$m=3$	$m=4$	$m \geq x$ and $n < 2^x$
$A_m(n)$	1	A000188	A000189	A000190	$L_2(n)$
$B_m(n)$	n	A008833	A008834	A008835	1
$C_m(n)$	n	A000188	A053150	A053164	1
$D_m(n)$	1	A007913	A050985	A053165	n
$E_m(n)$	1	A007913	A048798	A056555	$K_2(n)^m/n$
$F_m(n)$	1	A055491	A056551	A056553	$K_2(n)^m$
$G_m(n)$	1	A007913	A056552	A056554	$K_2(n)$
$H_m(n)$	n	A053143	A053149	A053167	$K_2(n)^m$
$J_m(n)$	n	A019554	A019555	A053166	$K_2(n)$
$K_m(n)$	1	A007947	A007948	A058035	n
$L_m(n)$	n	A003557	A062378	A062379	1

Further reading

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Multiplicative is not used here in the same sense as in S Tabirca, About Smarandache-Multiplicative Functions, American Research Press.